

CERTIFICATE

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

Ko'paysinova Zarifa Xamiddullo Qizi

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALIDA

ESSENTIAL FEATURES OF NOUN PHRASES IN MODERN ENGLISH AND LINGUOCULTURAL

ASPECTS OF THEIR TEACHING TO INTERMEDIATE

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir: A.A. Abdurahmonov

Яндекс

@mail

Google

2023/OKTABR